

STRUCTURAL CHANGES DURING PLASTIC DEFORMATION AT CRACK TIPS OF PVDF FILMS – A SEMI-QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

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Summary: On 200 μm thick α -Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) films double edge notched tension tests have been performed and the structural properties of the deformation zone were investigated using scanning small angle X-ray scattering (sSAXS) and scanning wide angle X-ray scattering (sWAXS) methods. PVDF is a semi-crystalline polymer exhibiting different polymorphous states, which can be transformed into each other. The polymorphs of highest interest are the most commonly observed α -phase and the piezoelectric β -phase. Scanning scattering methods allow the correlation of morphological properties of a specimen with the position on the sample. The crack tip region was scanned in two directions perpendicular to the X-ray beam with a spatial resolution of 0.2 mm. Changes in non-crystalline features (e.g. void formation, craze fibril formation and orientation) and the crystalline morphology and fine structure (e.g. phase transformation) in the crack tip plastic zone region were investigated in detail. It was found that the plastic zone ahead of the crack could be divided into 3 areas: the outer zone, characterized by the presence of cavities, a transition state with very strong cavitation and the mid-rip zone with β - PVDF fibers bridging a low density α -PVDF matrix.

Keywords: PVDF, notched fracture test, phase transition, SAXS, WAXS, scanning scattering techniques

INTRODUCTION

Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymer exhibiting at least four polymorphous states, referred to as α , β , γ and δ . The different crystalline morphologies allow for a broad range of properties and applications, which is particularly the case for α - and β -PVDF. While the α -form is used in a variety of applications with specific optical, chemical or electrical requirements, the β -form exhibits ferroelectric properties and is used e.g. for sensors. In terms of crystal structure, both modifications are orthorhombic [1]. The non-polar α -form is most commonly observed and obtained when the material is solidified from the melt by simple cooling procedures. The polar β -form is obtained among other routes by phase transformation from the α -modification by mechanical stretching of PVDF at elevated temperatures [2]. A potential new field of application for PVDF is in solar energy devices. For example, non-polar α -PVDF encapsulation foils are currently investigated for photovoltaic modules, which are multi-layer components of flexible and stiff materials [3]. In highly ductile materials such as PVDF significant plastic deformation zones

are formed in the highly stressed region ahead of a crack tip. On a local scale, these plastic deformation zones consist of highly stretched material in the formation of which phase transformation mechanisms may play a significant role. It is the aim of this paper to characterize the structural changes during plastic deformation at near crack tips in α -PVDF films. A combination of scanning wide angle X-ray scattering (scanning-WAXS) and small angle scattering (scanning-SAXS) is applied to obtain quantitative information on texture, crystallinity, phase composition and cavities. WAXS is widely used in polymer science to study crystallographic properties, SAXS is a powerful tool to characterize the morphology of semi crystalline polymers, like long period, lamellae thickness and, in addition, also the non crystalline properties like cavities and cracks. In order to analyze the phenomena occurring near the crack tip, it is essential to use these methods in a scanning mode and obtain maps of the deformed area with a spatial resolution in the sub-millimeter range. Recently, we have reported a phase transformation of α - to β -PVDF occurring during fibrillation of the polymer ahead of the crack tip [7]. In this work we summarize some of the results of this study and show complete maps of the plastic deformation zone of one crack from a symmetric DENT sample a PVDF foil tested in tension.

EXPERIMENTAL

The 200 μm thick α -PVDF foils with a melting peak temperature of 170°C studied in this paper were supplied by Solvay Advanced Polymers, France S.A, Paris-Cedex. The foils were produced by the supplier on a lab-scale extruder. Rectangular samples having a width of 30 mm and a length of 120 mm were cut parallel to extrusion direction. The foils were razor notched to obtain double edge notched tension (DENT) specimens with a ligament length of 12 mm. Tensile tests at ambient conditions (23°C, 50% rel. humidity) and a displacement rate of 10 mm/min were performed using an Instron tensile tester model 4505 with a 1 kN load cell. To describe the material morphology and the micromechanism of deformation of the as-delivered 200 μm thick double edge notched α -PVDF sample, the tensile test was stopped after complete plastic zone development and significant crack propagation. The samples were unloaded by opening the clamps of the tensile testing apparatus. For the X-ray measurements the unloaded samples were fixed on sample holder which allowed the controlled movement in the x-y plane perpendicular to the X-ray beam. sWAXS and sSAXS measurements were carried out on a Bruker NanoSTAR in transmission mode with X-rays from a rotating anode generator providing a radiation with a wavelength of 1.54 Å (Cu K α). The NanoSTAR was equipped with a 2D – position sensitive detector which could be placed in different distances from the sample. A sketch of the experiment is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Sketch of the measuring setup. The specimen (S) was mounted on a XY stage which could be moved with an accuracy of 2 μm . The plastic zone and the surrounding area was

scanned with a 0,1 mm in diameter beam. The detector (*D*) could be moved to different distances from the specimen. In WAXS mode *S-D* is ~ 6 cm in SAXS mode ~64 cm.

The sample to detector distance for the SAXS-measurements was 64 cm, for the WAXS measurements 6 cm. The distances were calibrated using a Ag-behenate reference sample for the SAXS-setup and Corund for the WAXS setup respectively. The diameter of the X-ray beam was approximately 100 μ m. The sample holder could be moved with a precision of 2 μ m in plane perpendicular to the beam.

The measuring protocol was as follows: In a first step in the SAXS mode, a radiograph of the specimen was taken. The radiograph was obtained by measuring the transmission of the specimen every 200 μ m in both directions. This was performed by placing a X-ray sensitive diode into the beam directly after it had penetrated the sample. The signal of the diode was proportional to the intensity of the x-ray transmitted through the sample. A special designed software [4] displayed the radiography and was used to select the measuring positions. For the WAXS measurements the sample was fixed on an additional sample holder, allowing to shorten the distance between the sample and detector down to 6 cm. Position marks on the holder ensured that the same measurement positions for both SAXS and WAXS were chosen. For the data interpretation and evaluation all scattering patterns were corrected for background scatter.

SAXS Data Analysis

For the determination of morphological parameters, isotropic SAXS patterns $I(q, \psi)$ were radially averaged with respect to ψ , yielding the $I(q)$ scattering curves, q being the scattering vector. They were analyzed applying a 1D correlation function method [5], to calculate the long period and the thickness of the crystal lamellae. Oriented SAXS patterns were reduced by averaging within arcs from $\psi = -15$ to 15 , where the main direction of the oriented signal was defined as $\psi = 0$. For fibril-like structures, a cross-sectional radius of gyration R_{gc} was derived using an exponential law, modified from the usual Guinier law [6]:

$$qI(q) = I_1 \exp(-q^2 R_{gc}^2 / 2) \quad (1)$$

where I_1 is the limit value of $qI(q)$ for $q \rightarrow 0$. Assuming a circular cross-section of the rod, the radius of the circle R_c is equivalent to $\sqrt{2} R_{gc}$. For plate like structures, we used a second type of modified Guinier law:

$$q^2 I(q) = I_2 \exp(-q^2 R_{g1}^2) \quad (2)$$

where I_2 is the limit value of $q^2 I(q)$ for $q \rightarrow 0$. R_{g1} is the one-dimensional "radius of gyration", simply given by $R_{g1} = D/\sqrt{12}$, where D is the height of the plates.

To image and quantify the predominant orientation of the structures within the sample at different measuring points, the q -averages from $I(q, \psi)$ were computed, yielding a function $I(\psi)$ of the polar angle ψ . Peaks in the $I(\psi)$ curve yield directly the predominant orientation of the structure elements rotated by 90° .

Scanning-WAXS Data Analysis

The WAXS patterns have been used to investigate phase compositions of the sample. The amount of different crystalline phases in a sample is directly related to the integral scattering intensity of the contributions from each phase. In the case of tested PVDF-samples the mass fraction of the β -phase (X^β) could be estimated using following considerations: The α -phase has the reflections $(100)^\alpha$, $(020)^\alpha$ and $(110)^\alpha$ in the region between $2\theta = 15-22^\circ$, 2θ being the scattering angle. In this area also the $(100)^\beta$ and $(200)^\beta$ reflections appear. In order to distinguish between α and β , we turn to the region $2\theta = 23-27^\circ$, where the $(021)^\alpha$ and $(120)^\alpha$ reflections do not overlap with contributions from the β -phase. A parameter $\rho\alpha$ was first calculated from the WAXS signal of undeformed (and isotropic) α -phase by the ratio

$$\rho^\alpha = \frac{I_{100}^\alpha + I_{020}^\alpha + I_{110}^\alpha}{I_{021}^\alpha + I_{120}^\alpha}$$

I_{100}^α and other similar expressions represent the integrated peak intensities. Calculating a similar intensity ratio for an α - β mixture, one obtains:

$$\rho^{\alpha+\beta} = \frac{I_{100}^\alpha + I_{020}^\alpha + I_{110}^\alpha + I_{012}^\beta + I_{120}^\beta}{I_{021}^\alpha + I_{120}^\alpha}$$

A rough estimate of the α/β phase ratio was obtained by the difference $\rho^{\alpha+\beta} - \rho^\alpha$ which is proportional to this phase ratio. As the proportionality constant is unknown, only relative changes in β content may be assessed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2 shows a micrograph of the investigated area of the sample and typical diffraction patterns. The plastic zone had an extension of approximately 1mm in height and a width over the hole sample. In the undeformed area (1) both, the SAXS and WAXS patterns exhibited isotropic scatter. This could be regarded to the spherulitic alignment of the lamellae crystals in α -PVDF. The long period and lamella thickness was determined to be 10.5nm and 3nm respectively and did not change significantly within the native area. At position (2), the edge of the plastic zone, a second contribution to the SAXS pattern, a vertical streak raised in the SAXS pattern. This signal indicated the formation of cavities, orientated perpendicular to the strain axis. The isotropic scatter from lamellae was still visible, there were no changes in lamellae morphology.

Fig. 2: Micrograph of the investigated area and sample diffraction patterns, arrows denote the corresponding positions on the sample. In the undeformed area (1) both, the WAXS and the SAXS pattern showed isotropic scattering (rings). At the edge of the plastic zone (2), an additional contribution, a vertical streak, raised in the center of the SAXS pattern, while the WAXS pattern kept its rings. In the central zone ahead of the crack tip (3), the SAXS pattern changed to a horizontally oriented elliptic streak, while the WAXS pattern mainly consisted of rings and two points in the equator of the pattern. The central zone near the crack tip (4) showed crossed streaks in the SAXS pattern and four points in the WAXS pattern.

This was confirmed by the WAXS pattern, showing only scatter contributions of the α -phase with no stress induced alignment. An explanation for that could be the possibility of stress relaxation in the material due to formation of cavities. At the area central plastic zone far away from the crack tip (3), the material had changed its morphology. The former isotropic scattering pattern had changed to an elliptic, indicating that fibrils, oriented parallel to the strain axis, had been formed. In the corresponding WAXS pattern an oriented scattering signal occurred, corresponding to the fibrous part of the sample. Simultaneous with the formation of the fibrils a partly α to β phase transition occurred, indicating that the fibrils were formed of β -PVDF, while the surrounding matrix consisted of α PVDF. The fibrils had a mean diameter of 15 ± 1 nm. There were no alignment or orientation effects within the α phase. In the central plastic zone near the crack tip (4) the fibers crossed each other. The diameter of the fibrils at pos. (4) was determined to be 11.5 ± 1 nm. The distribution of the β -phase within the sample was an indicator for the amount of fibrous material. The highest amount of β -phase was typically located near the crack tip. With rising distance from the tip the transformation zone became smaller. Additionally the mean orientation of the fibrils, as evaluated from the SAXS pattern, indicated with lines, is shown. In the transitional stage, when the cavities were formed, no phase transition occurred. The orientation of the fibrils indicated the direction of the main shear direction in the material during crack testing, according to the slip line theory [8]. The effect of crack tip blunting on the geometry of the slip field in near tip region leads to the formation of crossed shear directions. In the central area far away from the crack tip the fibers were parallel to the strain axis, near the crack the main force was nearly parallel to the notch, the fibers were tilted towards the notch surface.

A summary of the structural changes occurring in PVDF tested in a double notched crack test is sketched in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Sketch of the structural properties of the samples near the crack tips [7].

In a region, far away from the crack tip, orientated elongated cavities were formed. The orientation of the cavities was perpendicular to the strain axis. In this area neither a change in the long period, orientation nor phase transition occurred. In the mid-rip region fibrils were formed, and similar to that a phase transition from α to β PVDF occurred. The remaining α

PVDF kept its isotropic orientation while the β form was high orientated, forming fibrils. The β/α ratio increased when the fibrous structures become more and more dominant. At the crack tip occurred a nearly complete phase transition from α to β PVDF. This indicated that the fracture of the material was indeed controlled by the fracture behavior of very thin β -PVDF fibers.

CONCLUSION

The results show clearly the potential of position-resolved scattering methods in studying fracture processes in polymers. Morphological changes could be detected near crack tips in α -PVDF tested in tension as DENT samples and a model for crack propagation was proposed: The fracture of this material starts by the formation of cavities oriented orthogonal to the strain axis. Moreover, a partial phase transformation from α to β PVDF occurs in the plastic process zone. Most interestingly, the β -phase appears in fibrils oriented along the main shear directions within the sample, as predicted by the slip line theory. This β -fibrils are the further strained till failure of the material, which seems to be controlled by the behavior of these very thin β -PVDF fibers. There is the formation of cavities, fibrillation and phase transformation, which all help to dissipate energy and, hence, increase the toughness of the material.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Lovinger, A. J., In *Development in crystalline polymers 1*, ed.; Basset, D. C., Applied Science: London, **1982**; p 195 ff.
- [2] Kepler, R.G.; Anderson, R. A. *Advances in Physics* **1992**, 41, (1), 1-57.
- [3] Oreski, G.; Wallner, G.M.; Skringer, A.; Pertl, P.; Plessing, A. *EuroSun2004 – Proceedings* **2004**, 2, 2-883 - 2-888.
- [4] Fratzl, P.; Jakob, H. F.; Rinnerthaler, S.; Roschger, P.; Klaushofer, K. *J. Appl. Cryst.* **1997**, 30, 765-769.
- [5] Strobl, G.R.; Schneider, M.J.; *J. Polym. Sci.: Polym. Phys. Ed.* **1980**, 18, 1343-1359.
- [6] Fratzl, P. *J. Appl. Cryst.* **2003**, 36, 397-404.
- [7] G. A. Maier, G. Wallner, R. Lang, P. Fratzl, *Macromolecules*, accepted
- [8] Rice, J.R., Johnson, M.A., In *Inelastic behavior of solids*, ed.: Kanninen, M. F., McGraw-Hill: New York, **1970**, p 641-672